

Disaster Risk Reduction Management and School Safety in Bunawan District Schools

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Abstract. This study was purposely conducted to determine the extent of disaster risk reduction management in Bunawan District Schools and its school safety in the new normal during the school year 2021-2022. Non-experimental descriptive-correlational was used as the research design, with teachers as respondents from respective schools. Mean scores, standard deviation, Pearson r, and linear regression analysis were used to analyze the gathered data. Results showed that the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management implementation practices in Bunawan District are pervasive in directing, coordinating, evaluating, planning, and organizing, thus, highly noticeable among schools. School Safety was outstanding in managing school operations, home-school coordination, well-being and protection, and focusing on teaching and learning. Disaster Risk Reduction Management implementation strongly correlates positively and significantly with School Safety. Planning, Organizing, Coordinating, and Evaluating directly influence school safety. The study recommended that the Bunawan Public School District Supervisor may look to other factors that contribute to redirecting coordination and other significant activities and advocate significant indicators as policy inputs to newly appointed School Heads in the coming future. School Heads in Bunawan District may sustain the practices in intensifying the manner to propel teachers to do the same and attract stakeholders in their full participation. Other factors influencing schools' performance may be considered, such as not focusing on effective management and operation but on learners' improvement across learning areas.

KEY WORDS

1. disaster risk reduction and management
2. school safety
3. school operations

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1. Introduction

Dealing with disasters leads to more focused emergency response strategies. However, towards the end of the 20th century, it has been increasingly recognized that disasters are not natural even if it is associated with the hazard, and with this, this is only reducing and managing conditions of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability that we can prevent losses and alleviate the impacts of disaster. Since we cannot reduce the severity of natural hazards, the main opportunity for reducing risk lies in reducing vulnerability and exposure. Reducing these two components of risk requires identifying and reducing the underlying drivers of risk, which are particularly related to poor economic and urban development choices and practices, degradation

of the environment, poverty and inequality, and climate change, which create and exacerbate conditions of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Addressing these underlying risk drivers will reduce disaster risk, lessen the impacts of climate change, and, consequently, maintain the sustainability of development (Gokmenoglu, 2021). Across the globe, disaster risk reduction is a part of sustainable development, so it must involve every part of society, government, non-governmental organizations, and the professional and private sectors. It, therefore, requires a people-centered and multi-sector approach, building resilience to multiple, cascading, and interacting hazards and creating a culture of prevention and resilience (Baytiyeh, 2018). Successful disaster risk reduction results from the combination of top-down, institutional changes and strategies with bottom-up, local, and community-based approaches. Disaster and Risk Management programs should not be standalone but instead be integrated within development planning and practice since disasters indicate failed or skewed development, unsustainable economic and social processes, and ill-adapted societies. There is no 'one-size-fits-all' approach to DRM, but several approaches and frameworks have been effectively implemented to reduce disaster risk. However, before reducing risk, we need to understand the hazards and the exposure and vulnerability of people and assets to those hazards. In the Philippines, the status report DRRM 2019 provides a snapshot of the latest DRR progress the Philippines has achieved under the four priorities of the Sendai Framework. It also highlights some of the key challenges surrounding the issue of creating coherence among the critical global frameworks at the country level. It makes recommendations for strengthening the overall Disaster Risk Management (DRM) governance by government institutions and other national, sub-national, and local stakeholders (UNDRR, 2019). The Philippines has updated legal foundations for disas-

ter risk reduction and management, emphasizing response-centric interventions, disaster prevention preparedness, and mitigation activities. This has been complemented by local risk governance legislation since 2003 to enable the use of local calamity funds for disaster preparedness and mitigation. However, these were considered insufficient to support change at the local level (GoP, 2009, as cited by Rogayan and Dollete, 2020). This acknowledgment led to enacting the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (Republic Act 10121) as the country's foremost legal instrument and guiding policy framework driving DRRM momentum across various governance levels. In Zambales, people are aware of a typhoon as being moderately aware of a tsunami and storm surge. Regarding hazard level, respondents perceived a typhoon as 'very destructive,' and they understood a tsunami and storm surge to be 'strong.' The barrio community often practices disaster preparedness for earthquakes, strong typhoons, landslides, fires, floods, and volcanic eruptions. This provided insights into the crafting of a community extension program to be spearheaded by the university. Such a program accentuates the need for massive dissemination of information about disasters for local communities so they become more aware of the causes and consequences of disasters. The proposed curriculum integration and extension program may inform practitioners and policymakers in making sound decisions regarding disaster risk reduction and mitigation strategies (Rogayan Dollete, 2020). Davao City has experienced catastrophic flooding, causing property damage and loss of lives. Communities must build resiliency to respond to flooding and mitigate its negative impacts. City officials and leaders must regularly review and update their existing policies to address gaps and promote effective community engagement (Cayamanda Paunlgui, 2020). The Bunawan District's locality has changed over time in terms of its landforms.

Apart from earthquakes, since the beginning of infrastructure development, flash floods have been common whenever heavy rain falls in most areas of the locality and among schools, and this has a high chance of overflows from rivers and seaside schools. Reports of the high incidence of flash floods in some selected localities and schools, where school children were in danger and prone to dengue and other health risks. In the current times, disasters and risks were not only appreciated as environmental and natural calamities but also considered health risks given the phenomenon of COVID-19 and its variants, which affect the lives of humankind and, most of all, children's learning opportunities. This made the research conceptualize and explore the schools' safety in implementing DRRM among schools in the Bunawan district.

2. Methodology

This chapter presented the details of the method, its steps in data collection, and the study's conduct. The method of this section delivered the narratives of each process, such as the research design, respondents, instrumentation, procedure in the data gathering, ethical considerations, data analysis, and its tool in the management of data collection, analysis, interpretation, and yielding of implications. This shed light and insights into the statement of the problem used.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design. No experimental designs are research designs that examine social phenomena without direct manipulation of the conditions that the subjects experience. There was also no random assignment of subjects to different groups. As such, evidence that supports the cause-and-effect relationships is largely limited (Pallant, 2020). On the other hand, descriptive correlational studies describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them—moreover, Predictive Correlational Designs. Predictive correlational studies predict the variance of one or more variables based on the variance of another variable. Predictive research was chiefly concerned with predicting outcomes, consequences, costs, or effects. This type of research tries to extrapolate from analyzing existing phenomena, policies, or other entities to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). The researcher used the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique to achieve the study's objectives and gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) defined quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It was formed from a deductive approach where the emphasis was placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacked the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. This study examined the implementation of disaster risk reduction management among Elementary Schools in the Bunawan District in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and coordinating school safety in terms of managing school operations, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being, protection, and home-school coordination. These were quantitatively described and rated according to the study's principles and assumptions. Using the design

mentioned, it was assumed that variables and their indicators are substantially founded. The researcher's goal is to provide empirical evidence so that the presented hypothesis shall be correctly proven or, otherwise, may be rejected.

2.2. Research Respondents—The proposed study's respondents were the school heads and teachers of the nine elementary schools in the Bunawan District, situated in the second congressional district of Davao City. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling was appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that could be classified with ancillary information. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, 100 respondents were taken randomly from the respective elementary schools. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through an online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections in the locality, and they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and how these contributed to the whole cyclical process in the implementation of Disaster Risk reduction management. As much as possible, these respondents were oriented with DRRM Program Implementation in the respective schools and how they function and contribute to the learning outcomes given the new normal learning system during SY 2021-2022. The researcher further observed ethics in research, which paved the way for a respondent to decline, and thus, corresponding

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—Permission to conduct the study. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superinten-

forms of consent/decline were provided. In this manner, ethical standards of research as part of the policy of the Rizal Memorial Colleges were strictly followed; thus, observance of health protocol was likewise implemented based on the Executive Orders released by the city government of Davao to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This proposed research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the kinds of literature reviewed, and contents coming from the preliminary interviews and narratives with colleagues were found relevant to the reviews. Two parts consist of the extent of Elementary Schools' Disaster Risk Reduction Management in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and coordinating. These indicators were provided and described with statements that can be quantitatively measured based on the study's objectives. On the other hand, the effectiveness of implementation concerning people, resources, structure, and culture was measured by adapting a statement survey that can address the study's queries. The survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level (Pallant, 2010). Results yielded a Cronbach alpha of 0.879, depicting a high correlation between and among constructs. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of disaster risk reduction and management among schools in the Bunawan District. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

dent of Davao City Schools Division channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Bunawan District Elementary Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher informed the randomly selected respondents and

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretations

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of DRRM implementation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of DRRM implementation is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of DRRM implementation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of DRRM implementation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of DRRM implementation is not manifested

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretations

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4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of school safety is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of school safety is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of school safety is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of school safety is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of school safety is not manifested

soon prepared and created a Google sheet form to facilitate the data collection for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents who did not have access to the internet, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets shall be given to each of them. Once done, a link is sent, and right away, responses are expected to be generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. Moreover, currently, the City Government of Davao has declared a Level 1 alert for COVID-19; however, this can still not be taken into

full consideration in gathering data since risks were still observable, though it was moderate, if not low in level. The researcher then observes health protocols in distributing and collecting the questionnaire; thus, the survey is conducted online, where randomly selected respondents were given soft copies of the survey form through Google Sheets, where they can respond to the survey questions online. However, hard copies were given to the respondents for those who did not have connections. If the respondent declined participation in the survey, consent was given, thus highly compliant with

research ethics. Activities went on March 19-30, 2022, and were further collected last April 12-18, 2022. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Once the Google sheet provided to the respondents generated responses, the researcher sought assistance from the College Data Analyst/Statistician to collate, sort, and analyze the

data collected. The preliminary analysis results were then given to the thesis adviser for coaching in providing interpretations and implications of the study and further deepening the appreciation of the analysis to make the interpretations more meaningful.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of disaster risk reduction management in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and coordinating, and statement problem number two (2) on the level of effectiveness of implementation given elements such as people, resources, structure, and culture were used respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction signifi-

cant relationship between the extent of disaster risk reduction management in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and coordinating, and school safety. Regression Analysis was used to address problem number 4, stating indicators of the extent of disaster risk reduction management that significantly influence school safety (Pallant, 2000), and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discussed the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered through tabular and textual forms to provide clear information and sound discussion based on results. Implications of results are presented through various reviews presented, to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

The Summary of the Extent of DRRM in Bunawan District

Table 1 summarizes the extent of DRRM implementation in Bunawan District Schools. It

can be perceived that planning (4.48), organizing (4.46), directing (4.56), coordinating (4.56), and evaluating (4.55) are very extensive practices.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of DRRM in Bunawan District

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Planning	4.48	Very Extensive
Organizing	4.46	Very Extensive
Directing	4.56	Very Extensive
Coordinating	4.56	Very Extensive
Evaluating	4.55	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.52	Very Extensive

As Kulatunga, (2020) stated that management structure describes how a company organizes its management hierarchy. In almost all organizations, a hierarchy exists. It also determines how the roles, power, and responsibilities are assigned, controlled, and coordinated and how information flows between the different levels of management. An organizational structure is a system that outlines how certain activities are directed in order to achieve the goals of an organization. These activities can include rules, roles, and responsibilities. The organizational structure also determines how information flows between levels within the company. In this context, management is necessary in its implement-

ation since this can make or break the planned projects and activities thus jeopardizing its details and targets.

The Summary of the Extent of School Safety

Table 2 presents the summary of school safety. Results revealed that Bunawan District Schools are vapping a very extensive practice on school safety through managing school operations (4.51), home-school coordination (4.51), well-being and protection (4.48), and focusing on teaching and learning (4.47). This suggests that the lowest mean score falls on focusing on teaching and learning, but the tweak emphasizes school and community coordination.

Table 2. The Summary of the Extent of School Safety

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Managing school operations	4.51	Very Extensive
Focusing on teaching and learning	4.47	Very Extensive
Well-being and protection	4.48	Very Extensive
Home-school coordination	4.51	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.49	Very Extensive

Rogayan and Dollete (2020) conducted cross-sectional descriptive survey research to determine the extent of disaster awareness and preparedness of the barrio or barangay community from the five southern municipalities of Zambales, Philippines. Results revealed that most respondents were moderately aware of the different disasters occurring in the community. They are very aware of a typhoon but moderately aware of a tsunami and storm surge. In terms of hazard level, respondents perceived a typhoon to be 'very destructive', whilst they understood a tsunami and storm surge to be 'strong'. The barrio community often practices disaster preparedness for earthquakes, strong typhoons, landslides, fire, flood, and volcanic eruptions. Amongst residents of the barrios, a moderate correlation between their levels of dis-

aster awareness and disaster preparedness. This provided insights into the crafting of a community extension program to be spearheaded by the university. Such a program accentuates the need for massive dissemination of information about disasters for local communities so they become more aware of the causes and consequences of disasters.

The Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Disaster Risk Reduction Management and the Extent of School Safety in Bunawan District Schools

Table 3 tests a significant relationship between the extent of disaster risk reduction management and the level of school safety in Bunawan District Schools. It can be depicted that Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between DRRM practices ($r=0.892$;

p<.001) and school safety.

Table 3. A Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Disaster Risk Reduction Management and Level of School Safety in Bunawan District Schools

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Disaster Risk Reduction Management	0.892	<0.001	Significant	Reject H0

Note: Significant @ p<0.05

This gives empirical evidence to support that the posed null hypothesis stating there is no significant relationship between DRRM practices and school safety must be rejected; thus, it can be said that DRRM implementation and School Safety in Bunawan District are significantly correlated. However, realities would attest that public schools’ failure to emphasize the importance of established disaster management would exacerbate the negative impacts of the disaster on its stakeholders. The study of (Cornell Sheras, 1998), noted problematic situations in an actual school crisis response. Findings showed that problems were rooted in the failure of school authorities to recognize crises that, when left unaddressed, can trigger crisis events or worsen a situation, which, if early detected that a potential disaster is imminent, can lead to effective action and prevent or at least reduce its impact. Identified key problems that significantly hinder crisis management response success include but are not limited to failure of leadership, gaps in communication, teamwork, and collaboration among the personalities involved, and failure to assume full responsibility – leading to finger-pointing whom to blame. When these dire situations persist, they will undoubtedly worsen disaster impacts and put the lives of many in great danger if not rectified or addressed carefully. However, In China, as the scale and frequency of disasters continue to intensify, public administration programs in both China and the United States are increasingly

acknowledging the importance of integrating emergency management into public administration education. After briefly reviewing and comparing their respective emergency management systems, the authors described the development of emergency management in the field of public administration in both countries (Hu Zhang, 2020). Moreover, there is a significant debate about the appropriate governance structure in a disaster response. Complex disasters exhibit both networked and hierarchical characteristics. One challenge in disaster management is how to structure a response that reconciles the need for centralized coordination among varied responders while retaining the flexibility to adjust operations to quickly changing conditions mutually.

The disaster Risk Reduction Management that Significantly Influence School Safety in Bunawan District Schools

The preceding presentation discusses the results of the analysis of linear regression, where assumptions of linearity are considered given the Model Summary, the Analysis of Variance, and the Coefficients. Table 4 depicts the regression coefficient analysis of the significant influence on school safety when analyzed with disaster indicators of risk reduction and management. Moreover, Table 13 gives the coefficient (unstandardized) that can be put into the linear equation, $y = c + b \cdot x$; where y is the estimated dependent outcome variable (school safety) score; c is constant or intercept; b is

the regression coefficients in Planning, Organizing, Directing, Coordinating and Evaluating, and x is the score on the independent predictor variable. Among the indicators of DRRM of Implementation, Planning ($p < .001$); Organizing ($p < .001$); Directing ($p < .001$); and Evaluating ($p < .001$) indicate statistically significant to predict or influence School Safety to get into the

sustainability of its extensive implementation, thus advance is its level of practices (Pallant, 2018; Gujarati, 2006). This provides empirical evidence to show that the indicators of DRRM implementation practices in Bunawan District schools are among the best practices for improving the School Learning Environment, if not the best, during pandemics.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on the Significant Influence on Disaster Risk Reduction Management that Significantly Influences School Safety in Bunawan District Schools

Model	B	Beta	SE	p	Decision
<i>H (Intercept)</i>	4.467		0.054	< .001	
<i>H (Intercept)</i>	0.301		0.156	0.056	Accept H0
Planning	0.159	0.163	0.056	0.006	Reject H0
Organizing	0.221	0.241	0.065	< .001	Reject H0
Directing	0.115	0.130	0.072	0.111	Accept H0
Coordinating	0.440	0.461	0.076	< .001	Reject H0
Evaluating	0.451	0.453	0.077	< .001	Reject H0
R²	= 0.875				
F-value	= 196.625				
p-value	= <0.001				

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.875 suggests that the DRRM practices among schools in Bunawan District accounts 87.5 of the variance of School Safety. This provides empirical evidence that variability of School Learning Environment can be accounted and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under DRRM Practices among schools in Bunawan District. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (196.625) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$. This tells us that the model is significantly a better predictor of School safety. Thus, indicators of DRRM practices such as planning, organizing, coordinating, and evaluating significantly influence

school safety. Preparation of the School Disaster Management Plan by identifying hazards like earthquakes, landslides, fires, floods, cyclones, etc, looking into structural safety requirements of the school for various hazards (Cheng, 2021). The planning process enables agreements between individuals, agencies, and community representatives to meet communities' needs during disasters. The plan becomes an accessible record of the commitments made to perform certain actions and to allocate physical and human resources. Schools are responsible for not only teaching disaster management knowledge but also serving as evacuation shelters. If a disaster happens during school hours, schools must consider the risks that students

are exposed to and respond early to such an event. Being prepared can reduce fear, anxiety, and losses that accompany disasters (Potter et al., 2021). Given this, Mooney et al. (2021) presented a study that aimed to increase understanding of schools' contributions to children's recovery by examining how this core context fosters children's effective coping in a disaster. The schools in the study proved a stable, supportive environment for children providing routine, consistency, and a sense of safety and security. Teachers were a trusted source of support for children, and they coached children to cope. Teachers and schools also continually kept channels open between children and their families, including maintaining contact with parents during aftershocks to reassure them their children were safe. Peer contact was also important for children to share their experiences and gain support from one another. Principals considered welfare and put in place support mechanisms for staff and the children. Understanding how a school context and the relationships within that context promote effective coping in children facing a disaster is critical for developing more effective psychosocial support, and intervention strategies for children. In view of the school's key role, support to schools and teachers, including further training for education professionals, is needed throughout a disaster cycle if children's positive adaptation and coping is to be fostered. Moreover, Direen (2017) added that based on the belief that the nature of successful leadership needs to change in a post-disaster setting. Principals learned about leadership from these experiences, highlighting the stories of four participants. This indicates that successful school leadership in a crisis context relies on making good use of support networks and collaborative professional relationships, maintaining a solid link to one's core beliefs, being fully aware of the impact of your leadership, and responding accurately and with agility to constant change. Disaster Risk Reduction and Manage-

ment as implemented by the Department of Education. RA 10121 mandates the local DRRM bodies to encourage community, specifically youth, participation in disaster risk reduction and management activities, such as organizing quick response groups, particularly in disaster-prone areas, and including disaster risk reduction and management programs as part of youth programs and projects. DepEd Order 37, S 2015 directs the comprehensive disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) in Basic Education Framework. This is to guide DRRM efforts in the basic education sector towards resilience-building in offices and schools, and to ensure that quality education is continuously provided and prioritized even during disasters and emergencies. This has been institutionalized through its integration into the school curriculum. Section 14 of the Republic Act 10121 (or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010) requires DepEd, CHED, and Tesda to integrate disaster risk education in school curricula. The law said DepEd and CHED have an important part to play in the country's approach to DRRM. DepEd and CHED officials agreed, saying students and teachers must be equipped with knowledge on mitigating and managing hazards and risks brought by natural disasters like earthquakes. As a response, since the current events of the Philippine Educational System is the response action to COVID 19 virus, where DepEd mandated all schools to explore the possibility of conducting limited face to face classes through having school safety assessment tool. As part of the implementation of the progressive expansion of limited face-to-face classes amid the Covid-19 pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) has revised its School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT) and is currently finalizing the guidelines on the conduct of in-person learning (DepED memorandum no. 001, S 2021, dated September 15, 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings were based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The proposed study’s respondents were the school heads and teachers of the nine elementary schools in the Bunawan District, situated in the second congressional district of Davao City. The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. Bunawan District Elementary Schools exhibited very extensive implementation and practices in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in terms of directing (4.57), coordinating (4.56), evaluating (4.56), planning (4.48), and organizing (4.46), suggesting effective implementation. Bunawan District Schools exhibited extensive school safety in terms of managing school operations (4.51), home-school coordination (4.51), well-being and protection (4.48), and focusing on teaching and learning (4.47), which suggests outstanding. The DRRM implementation and practices significantly correlate with School Safety ($r= 0.892$; $p<0.001$), resulting in a significantly high correlation. Disaster Risk Reduction Management indicators in terms of planning ($p<0.006$), organizing ($p<0.001$), coordinating ($p<0.001$), and evaluating ($p<0.001$) indicate statistically significant predictors to influence high school safety.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions, to wit; The Disaster Risk Reduction and Management implementation practices in Bunawan District are very extensive in terms of directing, coordinating, evaluating, planning, and organizing, thus, highly noticeable among schools. School Safety was outstanding in managing school operations, home-school coordi-

nation, well-being and protection, and focusing on teaching and learning. Disaster Risk Reduction Management implementation strongly correlates positively and significantly with School Safety. Planning, Organizing, Coordinating, and Evaluating directly influence school safety.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; The Bunawan Public School District Supervisor may consider other factors that contribute to redirecting coordination and other significant activities and advocate for significant indicators as policy inputs to newly appointed School Heads in the future. This was why disaster risk reduction was important. It lowers the probability that a hazard or man-made event has disastrous consequences. Disaster risk reduction in education equips people with the knowledge and skills to reduce the impact of natural hazards by lessening the number of fatalities, limiting the amount of damages, and decreasing disruption to economic, social, and cultural activities School Heads in Bunawan District may sustain the practices by intensifying them, propelling teachers to do the same, and attracting stakeholders to their full participation. Other factors that may influence schools’ performance, such as focusing less on effective management and operation and more on learners’ improvement across learning areas, may be considered. Future research may include the underlying empirical investigations on the process and mechanism of schools’ monitoring systems to enhance and be included in the planning process cycle, implementation steps, and evaluation mechanisms.

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